

DEVELOPMENT OF A MODE III TEST RIG FOR COMPOSITE LAMINATES AND SANDWICH FACE/CORE FRACTURE CHARACTERIZATION

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work consists in developing a novel test rig, which is inspired by the Shear Torsion Bending (STB) rig designed for unidirectional composites. The test rig is capable to carry out fracture characterization tests on pre-delaminated composite sandwich specimens subjected to external out-of-plane shear loadings. Boundary conditions and specimen geometry have been designed in order to induce an out-of-plane stress state as uniform as possible along the debond front. Theoretical and numerical analyses of the specimen enable the understanding of how specimen geometrical parameters and loads introduction influence stress and energy release rate G distributions along the debond front.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures are considered as key enablers for future and present lightweight structural applications in naval ships because of their superior stiffness/weight and strength/weight ratios compared with traditional metallic concepts as well as monolithic composite materials. Naval vessels are expected to encounter a large variety of load scenarios, which can cause different types of damages within the sandwich structure [1].

The most common and severe type of damage a composite sandwich structure can experience is the lack of adhesion between the face sheets and the core commonly known as a “debond”. Therefore, fracture characterization of the face/core interface is fundamental for the prediction of the remaining life of a damaged sandwich structure.

The aim of this work consists in developing a test rig which is able to carry out fracture characterization of a delaminated or debonded specimen (monolithic or sandwich composite specimen respectively) under mode III loading.

Different experimental methods have been developed for evaluating G_c under out-of-plane loading; they include the edge crack torsion [2] (ECT), the modified split cantilever beam (MSCB) [3] and the shear bending torsion (SBT) [4] tests. The ECT, MSCB and the STB tests have been developed for monolithic composite laminates. Furthermore, some problems remain with interpretation of the results and the data reduction method used from both the ECT and MSCB tests [5-9].

The STB test method [4] seems to offer an innovative and reliable solution for performing fracture characterization tests of monolithic laminates under mode III conditions. In [4] G is extracted from the FE model for different types of composite laminates using the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT). These numerical results show that the distribution of the energy release rate G is close to the uniformity along the debonded front for all the experimental load scenarios tested. Thus, the STB appears to address many issues of concern for other existing fracture test methods for composite laminates.

2 METHOD

The specimen geometry is presented in fig. 1. The width in the delaminated region is b and the width of the intact region ahead of the crack front is W . W is therefore the geometrical parameter related to the crack surface when the crack is propagating of a quantity Δa . The two faces have the same thickness t_f and the crack length a is the distance between the end of the load tab and the crack tip. L is the total specimen length and h_{tab} is the height of each load-tab. An out-of-plane load P , or the corresponding displacement Δ , is applied to the specimen through the lower load-tab. Two longitudinal edge cuts (LCs) fig. 1c are added in order to mitigate free-edge effects, when an external out-of-plane load is applied [4, 8].

Figure 1a, b, c: Specimen scheme and boundary conditions.

Figure 2a, b: Test rig overview (a) and detail of the specimen, load blocks and load tabs (b).

A complete overview of the test rig is provided in fig. 2a, b. The specimen with the load-tabs is placed on a T-slot table and a bi-axial AT-858 MTS test machine is used to carry out the tests. The external moment M_x in the y-direction is physically applied through the machine hydraulic actuator. A linear ball bearing allows the free translation along the y-axis. An additional hydraulic actuator is clamped on the T-slot machine table and it applies the out-of-plane load P on the specimen.

The boundary conditions and the external load P are introduced on the specimen following the illustration shown in fig. 3. Two rigid surfaces are created at the two load tab surfaces, using multiple point constraints: two reference points are connected rigidly to all the element nodes lying on the mentioned surfaces. In this way, loads and boundary conditions are transferred directly from these two reference points to all the nodes belonging to the load tab surfaces. All the degrees of freedom of the reference point 1 are set equal to zero. All the degrees of freedom of the reference point 2 are set equal to zero except translations along the y-axis.

FE analyses of the test specimen have driven the design of the test rig geometry and how the test rig applies loads and boundary conditions to the specimen. Specifically, the distribution of the energy release rate along the crack front has been first studied for a specified sets of external loads and boundary conditions. Then, the geometrical specimen dimensions have been sized in order to achieve an out-of-plane stress state as uniform as possible along the crack front.

The numerical model is built in Abaqus 2016 and it consists of one cracked specimen and the two load tabs, which are tied to the cracked ends of the specimen.

Figure 3: Boundary conditions and load applied to the FE model.

The numerical analyses are carried out for a composite laminate, in order to compare the results with the ones in [4], and for a composite sandwich configuration. The face-sheets of the composite sandwich consist in a quasi-isotropic lay-up of GFRP sheets. The core is a closed cell PVC foam with a density of $80 \text{ [kg/m}^3\text{]}$. Material properties are listed in Table 1. All materials are modelled as orthotropic with a linear elastic behavior. The material chosen for the load tabs is steel (considered isotropic) with a young modulus $E = 209 \text{ GPa}$ and a Poisson Ratio $\nu=0.3$.

Material	Elastic Moduli [GPa]						Poisson's ratios		
	E ₁₁	E ₂₂	E ₃₃	G ₁₂	G ₁₃	G ₂₃	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
GFRP (-45, 90, 45, 0)	18.6	9.5	18.0	2.7	6.1	2.8	0.370	0.400	0.430
Divinycell PVC H80	0.095	0.095	0.095	0.027	0.027	0.027	0.4	0.4	0.4

Table 1: Material properties used in the numerical analysis. The GFRP properties have been assumed as in [11-12].

The mesh used in the FE model has been presented in [1], where a similar model has been formulated to derive the fracture parameters using the Crack Surface Displacement Extrapolation (CSDE) method. The CSDE method uses the equations derived by Suo in [13] to describe the local displacement field at the crack tip. The mesh at the crack tip is shown in fig. 1. Since, the FE model is a 3D model (and a very refined mesh is needed at the crack tip to apply the CSDE method) a sub-modelling technique is adopted for each analysis. Accordingly, with the sub-modelling technique, a model having a coarse mesh is run and secondly only the crack tip zone is analyzed using a finer mesh. The displacements found as results of the coarse model are applied to the sub-model. The smallest element size used in the sub-model is equal to 3 μm in order to accurately capture the displacement field near the crack tip.

In order to understand and explain the numerical results and to develop a data reduction technique, an analytical model is also being developed. An expression of the global energy release rate has been obtained for a monolithic laminate which highlights the different contributions, due to the external and internal forces and moments, and to the near crack-front deformations on varying the specimen geometry.

In the model, the two cracked arms are treated as two Timoshenko beams subjected to the loads and boundary conditions applied in the numerical model. The materials are assumed as quasi-isotropic in the yz-plane and linear elastic.

The two arms are subjected out-of-plane shear, bending moment and torsional moment. The delaminated arms are partially clamped at $Z = 0$ where two springs with stiffnesses equal to k_r and k_t are added to the Timoshenko beam in order to describe the compliance of the material at and ahead of the the crack front.. The rotational spring (k_r) models the crack root tip rotations, while the transverse spring k_t models the shear deformation of the uncracked part of the specimen. The torque moment produces a non-uniform torsion of the beam since warping is not allowed at one beam end at $Z = -a$. Once the analytical equation of the beam compliance $C = \Delta/P$ is found, the Irwin-Kies equation can be used to compute the analytical expression for the energy release rate:

$$\mathcal{G} = \frac{P^2}{2W} \cdot \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied load, W is the reduced specimen width, C is the beam compliance and a is the crack length.

3 RESULTS

Numerical results highlight why it is necessary to add longitudinal cuts (LCs) in order to have a uniform out-of-plane stress state along the crack front. Hence, using the numerical results it is possible to understand which geometrical parameters influence the energy release rate distribution along the crack front. The test rig has been designed based on these results.

The influence of the longitudinal edge cuts is studied comparing the effect of their magnitude on the energy release rate distribution along the crack front. Two FE analyses have been run: in the first analysis, the LCs are not present, and in the second analysis the LCs are added. The assumed geometry is: $t_f = 2 \text{ mm}$, $b = 30 \text{ mm}$, $W = 26 \text{ mm}$, $L = 160 \text{ mm}$, $L_{tab} = 60 \text{ mm}$, $h_{tab} = 10 \text{ mm}$.

The graph in fig. 4 shows on the horizontal axis the normalized coordinate s that runs along the crack front and on the vertical axis the ratio between the local mode III energy release rate component \mathcal{G}_{III} and the total value $\mathcal{G}_{tot} = \mathcal{G}_I + \mathcal{G}_{II} + \mathcal{G}_{III}$ of the energy release rate calculated using the local quantities.

Figure 4: Energy release rate distribution for along the s -coordinate running along the crack front width for the unidirectional GFRP laminate.

It can be seen (dotted line) that without the longitudinal cuts the amount of G_{III} at the specimen free edges ($s/W=0$ and $s/W=1$) is approximately 60% of the total local energy release rate G_{tot} . This means that the crack experiences different mode-mixity ratios, between mode I-II and mode III, along its width even if the macroscopic external load is a pure out-of-plane load, as it is shown in fig. 1. On the other hand, the local distribution of G_{III} is more uniform with the introduction of the longitudinal cuts and G_{III} is approximately 86% of the total local energy release rate G_{tot} at the crack edges ($s/W=0$ and $s/W=1$).

The analytical values of G derived with equation (1) can describe effectively the mechanical behavior of the specimen. The plot in figure 5 shows good agreement between the analytical dimensionless energy release rate calculated with equation (1) and the energy release rate calculated from the numerical model using the compliance method.

Figure 5: Comparison between analytical and numerical dimensionless ERRs vs. different crack sizes.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work a numerical and analytical study is presented in order to investigate and understand the effects of the geometrical parameters on the energy release rate distribution along the specimen crack front in monolithic composite laminates. This test set up makes it possible to introduce an out-of-plane load and boundary conditions that induce a uniform and predominant G_{III} distribution along the specimen crack front. The same test rig configuration is currently being studied for sandwich specimens.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Christian Berggreen. *Damage Tolerance of Debonded Sandwich Structures*. PhD thesis, Technical University of Denmark, 2004.
- [2] Lee SM. An edge crack torsion method for mode III delamination fracture testing, *J Compos Technol, Res* 1993;**15(3)**:193-201.
- [3] Szekrényes A. Improved analysis of the modified split-cantilever beam for mode-III fracture, *Int J Mech Sci* 2009;**51(9-10)**:682-93.
- [4] Barry D. Davidson, Felipe O. Sediles, Mixed mode I-II-III delamination toughness determination via shear-torsion-bending test, *Composites Part A-applied Science and Manufacturing* — 2011, Volume **42** Issue 6, pp. 589-603.
- [5] Ratcliffe JG. Characterization of the edge crack torsion (ECT) test for mode III fracture toughness measurement of laminated composites, NASA-TM-2004-213269; 2004.
- [6] De Morais AB, Pereira AB, De Moura MFSF, Magalhaes AG. Mode III interlaminar fracture of carbon/epoxy laminates using the edge crack torsion (ECT) test, *Compos Sci Technol* 2009;**69(5)**:670–6.
- [7] Pennas D, Cantwell WJ, Compston P. The influence of strain rate on the mode III interlaminar fracture of composite materials, *J Compos Mater* 2007;**41(21)**:2595–614.
- [8] Robinson P, Song DQ. The development of an improved mode III delamination test for composites, *Compos Sci Technol* 1994;**52(2)**:217–33.
- [9] Ciccì D, Sharif F, Kortschot MT. Data reduction for the split cantilever beam mode III delamination test. Fatigue and fracture, *In: Proceedings of the 10th International conference on composite materials*, vol. 1. (ICCM-10), British Columbia; Canada; August 14–18 1995. p. 189–96.
- [10] Reeder, J. R. and Crews, J. H. J., “Redesign of the Mixed-Mode Bending Delamination Test to Reduce Nonlinear Effects,” *Journal of Composites Technology and Research*, Vol 14, 1992, pp. 12-19.
- [11] Standard Test Method for Tensile Properties of Polymer Matrix Composite Materials, *ASTM D3039/D3039M – 17*.

- [12] Standard Test Method for Shear Properties of Composite Materials by V-Notched Rail Shear Method, *ASTM D7078/D7078M – 12*.
- [13] Z. Suo. Singularities Interfaces and Cracks in Dissimilar Anisotropic Media. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 427(1873):331-358, February 1990. ISSN 1364-5021.